

1 **Tsunami generation potential of a strike-slip fault tip in the westernmost Mediterranean.**
2 **The case of the Averroes Fault.**

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19

20 **Abstract**

21 Tsunamis are triggered by sudden seafloor displacements, and usually originate from
22 seismic activity at faults. Nevertheless, strike-slip faults are usually disregarded as major
23 triggers, as they are thought to be capable of generating only moderate seafloor deformation;
24 accordingly, the tsunamigenic potential of the vertical throw at the tips of strike-slip faults is not
25 thought to be significant. We found the active dextral NW-SE Averroes Fault in the central
26 Alboran Sea (westernmost Mediterranean) has a historical vertical throw of up to 5.4 m at its
27 northwestern tip corresponding to an earthquake of Mw 7.0. We modelled the tsunamigenic
28 potential of this seafloor deformation by Tsunami-HySEA software using the Coulomb 3.3 code.
29 Waves propagating on two main branches reach highly populated sectors of the Iberian coast
30 with maximum arrival heights of 6 m within 21 and 35 min, which is too quick for current early-
31 warning systems to operate successfully. These findings suggest that the tsunamigenic potential
32 of strike-slip faults is more important than previously thought, and should be taken into account
33 for the the re-evaluation of tsunami early-warning systems.

34

35 **Introduction**

36 Tsunamis, catastrophic natural hazards that pose a significant threat to major
37 infrastructure and many densely populated coastal regions, are generated by the rapid
38 deformation of the seafloor due to fault or landslide activity^{1,2,3,4}. Seismic strike-slip faults do not
39 significantly displace the seafloor in flat-lying and smooth areas, and are therefore not generally
40 considered as potential triggers of tsunamis^{5,6}. Yet, tsunamis triggered by strike-slip faults have
41 been reported worldwide as a result of either vertical seafloor displacements in over-steepened
42 areas (e.g., the 1994 Mindoro earthquake⁷) and on restraining and releasing bends (the 1906 San
43 Francisco earthquake^{8,9} and events in other areas of southern California²), or seismogenic
44 submarine landslides (the 2010 Haiti earthquake¹⁰). The triggers of other historical strike-slip
45 earthquake-related tsunamis, such as the 1999 Izmit tsunami¹¹ and the 2012 and 2016 tsunamis
46 in the Indian Ocean¹², remain unknown. To date, despite the noteworthy vertical offsets at the
47 tips of strike-slip faults, these faults have not been considered a main tsunamigenic source.

48 The strike-slip Averroes Fault is located in the Alboran Sea (westernmost Mediterranean
49 Sea), which has been a tectonically active basin since the late Miocene¹³ (Fig. 1). The Alboran
50 Sea is deformed by strike-slip faults under laterally unlocked tectonic indentation driven by
51 Eurasian-African plate convergence¹⁴ at a rate of 4.5 mm/yr¹⁵ (Fig. 1) The Alboran Sea, whose
52 Iberian coast annually receives the highest number of tourists from all of Europe, has been
53 historically afflicted by tsunamis^{16,17,18}. Historical records show the simultaneous occurrence of
54 tsunamis striking the Adra and Malaga coasts at 365 CE¹⁶. However, little is known about the
55 tsunamigenic potential of the faults in this basin.

56 To resolve this problem, we identified the NW-SE dextral Averroes Fault as the structure
57 in the fault system with the strongest evidence of recent and active seafloor offset at its northern
58 termination (Figs. 1b, c and 2). Subsequent modelling the tsunamigenic potential of this structure
59 reveals the potential for tsunami generation triggered by vertical offset at the tip of a strike-slip
60 fault, providing knowledge crucial for reviewing potential tsunami hazards related to strike-slip
61 faults worldwide.

62
63 **Figure 1. The Averroes Fault in the tectonic framework of the Alboran Sea.** a) Location of
64 the study area; b) Multibeam bathymetric map displaying the main NNE-SSW shear zone

65 seismicity (red dots) and main tectonic features and seamounts; c) detailed tectonic map of the
66 central Alboran Sea highlighting the presence of the Averroes Fault northern segment in red and
67 southern segment in orange. Modified from Estrada et al. (2018)¹⁴. Legend: ACh, Alboran
68 Channel; AR, Alboran Ridge; AB, Algarrobo Bank; DB, Djibouti Bank; DVB, Djibouti Ville
69 Bank; IBB, Ibn Batouta Bank; CD, Campo de Dalias; YF, Yusuf Fault; AIF, Al Idrisi Fault;
70 AvF, Averroes Fault; and CSF, Carboneras-Serrata Fault. Red arrow indicates direction of
71 tectonic indentation.

72

73 **Results**

74 **The strike-slip Averroes Fault**

75 The Averroes Fault is a component of the NW-SE conjugate dextral strike-slip fault set of
76 the main NNE-SSW shear zone crossing the Alboran Sea¹⁴ (Fig. 1b). The Averroes Fault, which
77 is predominantly affected by shallow earthquakes at present (up to 15 km deep¹⁹), has a steeply
78 dipping main fault surface with a length of 38 km (Figs. 1b, c and 2) that splits upward into two
79 faults surfaces, the eastern one being currently deforming the seafloor (Fig. 2a).

80

81 **Figure 2. Seismic profiles illustrating the Averroes Fault.** a)
 82 Airgun seismic profile showing the deep structure. Legend:
 83 purple line corresponds with top of Miocene and blue line with
 84 base of Quaternary. Horizontal and vertical scale respectively
 85 in metres and seconds, two-way travel time (twtt). Vertical
 86 exaggeration x8.7; b) Parametric TOPAS profile (ultra-high-
 87 resolution) illustrating the upper reach (75 m) of the Averroes
 88 Fault. Inlet shows chronostratigraphic boundaries and fault
 89 events over the last 124,060 years. Red arrows indicate co-
 90 seismic wedges. Horizontal scale in metres and vertical scale
 91 in seconds (twtt). Vertical exaggeration x12.4.

92

93 The main Averroes Fault comprises two main segments: the southern segment (16 km
 94 long) horizontally displaces the seafloor surface by 4.1 km with dextral kinematics, while its

95 northern segment (22 km long) has a maximum vertical offset of 470 m at its tip (Fig. 2a), with a
96 northeastern downthrown block that creates a half-graben-like feature (Figs. 1c and 2). Tectonic
97 activity initiated along the Averroes Fault during the late early Pliocene^{20,21,22,23}, giving it an age
98 of 4.57 Ma^{24,20}. Considering the age of the fault and the vertical offset along its northern
99 segment, we calculate an average vertical slip rate of 0.1 mm/yr.

100 Activity of the Averroes Fault is driven by the tectonic inversion of the central Alboran
101 basin¹⁴. This activity has a co-seismic character evidenced in our ultra-high-resolution parametric
102 seismic profiles by interbedded sedimentary wedges (up to 4.5 to 5.4 m thick) vertically stacked
103 which represent mass-wasting events coming from the upthrown block (Fig. 2b). We have
104 established a chronostratigraphic control of activity spanning the last 124,000 yr (Fig. 2b). From
105 young to old, four events can be seen, with fault throws of 3.7 (seafloor), 5.4, 5.4 and 4.5 m
106 (unloaded successive fault offsets), and with ages of recent, 20,590 yr, 63,350 yr and 124,060 yr,
107 respectively (Fig. 2b and Suppl. Fig. 1). We therefore propose an approximate average
108 recurrence period of approximately 31,000 yr.

109

110 **Seafloor deformation and tsunamigenic potential**

111 Next, we modelled the tsunamigenic potential of the vertical seafloor offsets related to
112 the fault tip of the NW segment of the Averroes strike-slip Fault. Although seafloor deformation
113 may also occur by horizontal displacement of slope areas in the southern segment, it would be
114 reasonable to assume that horizontal displacement away from the tip might not lead to significant
115 vertical offset.

116 We employed Okada's approach^{25,26} to calculate deformation, by determining a
117 displacement on the fault plane of the SW (uplifted) block equal to one-half of the net slip; i.e.,
118 the displacement of the SW block was equivalent in magnitude to the displacement of the NE
119 (downthrown) block. We modelled a rapid co-seismic displacement of the seafloor considering a
120 vertical fault with a length of 22 km extending to a depth of 10 km and a uniform net slip of 5.4
121 m (with the NE block downthrown). This net slip corresponds to the historical maximum throw,
122 and was determined for two of the four events mentioned above. Our model suggests a
123 corresponding seismic moment equal to 3.88×10^{26} dyn/cm and an earthquake magnitude of Mw
124 7. Both the vertical and the horizontal computed deformations are depicted in Figure 3, which
125 demonstrates that deformation lobes affect both fault blocks with vertical displacements of 0.1 m
126 even at distances (perpendicular to the fault plane) of 17 km for the simulated Mw 7.0 event
127 (Fig. 3). The maximum horizontal displacements perpendicular to the fault plane are on the order
128 of 1.7 m.

129

130 **Figure 3. Seafloor deformation.** Computed deformation pattern of the crust affected by
 131 the Averroes Fault for a vertical offset of 5.4 m and an associated magnitude of Mw 7.
 132 a) Seafloor plan view: red indicates downthrow and blue indicates uplift; b) Vertical
 133 section: red line represents the Averroes Fault trace.

134

135 Next, we modelled the tsunami generation that might occur as a result of a vertical throw
 136 of 5.4 m on the northern segment of the Averroes Fault, using the non-linear hydrostatic shallow-
 137 water model Tsunami-HySEA applied to a high-resolution ambient grid (~50 m). We identified a
 138 heterogeneous tsunami propagation pattern, comprising two branches orthogonal to the fault
 139 trace; the main branch directed to the NE and the minor one directed to the SW (Fig. 4a and
 140 Suppl. Video 1). The NE branch has a straight path, and reaches land in the area of Campo de
 141 Dalías (Fig. 4a, Suppl. Fig. 2 and Suppl. Videos 2 and 3); a positive wave with maximum height
 142 (6 m) and shortest arrival time (21 min) occurs near the village of Balerna (Figs. 4a, c and
 143 Suppl. Video 2). In contrast, the SW branch initially corresponds to deep waters, and the
 144 propagating tsunami impinges against three elongated seamounts acting as morphological
 145 barriers, namely, the relatively long ENE-WSW Alboran Ridge, the E-W Ibn Batouta and three
 146 seamounts aligned NW-SE (Algarrobo, Djibouti and Djibouti Ville banks) (Figs. 1a, 4a and
 147 Suppl. Video 1). This impingement modifies the tsunami propagation path, forcing it to split into
 148 three subbranches directed to the NW and approximately to the W and S. The former reaches the
 149 Málaga coast with a wave height of up to 2 m and an arrival time of up to 35 min (Fig. 4a, Suppl.
 150 Fig.2 and Suppl. Video 4), whereas the latter reaches landfall along the Moroccan coast, in
 151 locations such as Ras Tarf cape (wave height 1 m; arrival time 21 min), Punta Negri (wave
 152 height 1 m; arrival time 20 min) and the new Nador Harbour (Port Nador West Med) (wave
 153 height 1 m; arrival time 27 min) (Fig. 4a, Suppl. Fig. 2 and Suppl. Video 1).

154

155
 156 Figure 4. **Modelled tsunami for the Averroes Fault.** a) Tsunami propagation
 157 considering a vertical offset of 5.4 m and an associated magnitude of Mw 7.
 158 Colour scale represents wave heights in metres and contours represent first arrival
 159 times in minutes. The highest wave heights and their arrival times impacting
 160 coastal localities are shown in the inset table. b) Balerma tsunami water-level
 161 inundation. Colour scale in meters. c) Tsunami wave height at Balerma control
 162 point based on seasurface time series simulated by Tsunami-HySEA.

163
 164 **Discussion**

165 After an earthquake strikes, it is crucial for early-warning systems to issue a rapid
 166 assessment while minimizing false alerts, based on the event magnitude, focal mechanism and
 167 potential tsunamigenic trigger.

168 The Averroes Fault in the Alboran Sea (Fig. 1a and b) with offsets that can reach 5.4 m
 169 (Fig. 2), suggesting earthquake magnitudes up to Mw 7, provides a fundamental opportunity to
 170 analyze this tsunamigenic mechanism, namely, the vertical offset of the seafloor concentrated at
 171 the northern fault tip.

172 Our modelling of tsunami propagation related to seafloor deformation along the Averroes
 173 Fault (Fig. 4 and Suppl. Video 1) provides a means to assess the potential tsunamigenic hazard
 174 of strike-slip fault tips. The propagation of tsunami is controlled by fault kinematics⁵ and we

175 found that the vertical throw at the tip of the Averroes Fault determines the onset of positive and
176 negative waves. The vertical deformation lobe of the NE downthrown block triggers an initial
177 negative wave followed by a striking positive wave raising up to 6 m above the usual water level
178 at Balerna coast (Fig. 4 and Suppl. Video 2). Contrasting, the vertical deformation of the SW
179 uplifted block forms an initial positive wave with a remarkable negative wave dropping up to 1.5
180 m in Malaga and 1.5 m in Moroccan coasts, and wave trains with significant withdrawal in both
181 areas (Suppl. Fig. 2).

182 The propagation of tsunami is also controlled by the interplay between fault orientation
183 and seafloor morphology^{5,6}, and we found that the NW-SE-oriented Averroes Fault focuses
184 waves mainly towards the NE and, to a lesser extent, the SW. The NE branch is predicted to
185 cross an area of smooth bathymetry, enabling linear propagation towards the Campo de Dalías
186 coast, which is characterized by tourist beaches and dominated inland by greenhouse agriculture
187 (Fig. 4 and Suppl. Video 1); likewise, the coastal proximity of the villages of Balerna,
188 Almerimar and Adra, and the short propagation time increase their vulnerability to tsunamis
189 (Fig. 4, Suppl. Fig.2 and Suppl. Videos 2 and 3). The NW subbranch focuses the highest waves
190 towards the Malaga coast, which exhibits a moderate tsunami hazard that may affect
191 infrastructures and beaches (Fig. 4, Suppl. Fig. 2 and Suppl. Videos 1 and 4). Moreover, the
192 coastline in this region becomes densely populated in summer, with large stretches of beach that
193 can be fully occupied. Meanwhile, the S subbranch influences the Moroccan coast, but to a lesser
194 extent (Fig. 4, Suppl. Fig. 2 and Suppl. Video 1).

195 Our findings demonstrate the need to reevaluate tsunamigenic hazards related to strike-
196 slip fault tips. Such faults are found predominantly in marine areas related to transform plate
197 boundaries, such as the northern San Andreas Fault²⁷ and the northeastern Caribbean plate²⁸, as
198 well as small seas, such as the Marmara Sea²⁹. Likewise, vertical offsets at fault tips may be
199 found along strike-slip faults related to segmented subduction zones, such as the Nazca plate
200 below the Ecuador-Colombia segment of the South American plate margin³⁰. All the mentioned
201 examples, are similar enough to the Averroes Fault and might also pose a significant threat to the
202 local population.

203 Here, we demonstrate that following a seismic event, vertical offset at the NW tip of the
204 Averroes Fault has the potential to generate destructive tsunamis in the westernmost
205 Mediterranean, with rapid arrival times at densely populated coastlines (21 min) that are too
206 short for existing early-warning systems to operate properly. Moreover, this study highlights the
207 need for coastal communities worldwide to review the tsunamigenic potential of strike-slip faults
208 through vertical offsets near their tips as a new tsunamigenic mechanism that may be of great
209 importance along transform and segmented convergent plate boundaries characterized by
210 submarine strike-slip faults. These findings justify the necessity of considering the tsunamigenic
211 hazard potential of strike-slip faults to improve the accuracy of tsunami early-warning systems in
212 geodynamic contexts of tectonic indentation, transform plate boundaries and subduction zones.

213

214

215 **Methods**

216 **Marine geophysics**

217 The geologic history and structure of the Averroes Fault were studied by means of
218 seismic profiles and swath bathymetric data. The seismic profiles come from the following 17
219 cruises: AS, CONOCO Cab-01, R/V Robert D. Conrad cruise, DBS, EAS, Fauces, Fauces-1bis,
220 GC-83-2, GC-90-1, GC-90-2, He-91-3, RRS Charles Darwin cruise, Marsibal, Montera, RAY,
221 SAGAS, (<http://gma.icm.csic.es/sites/default/files/geoweb/OLsurveys/index.htm>). The cruises
222 were independent to this study, except 4 of them (Montera, GC-90-1, SAGAS, Fauces-1) where
223 the surveys of the Averroes Fault was included in the cruise objectives and provided new and
224 relevant information; these 4 cruises were led by scientists of the Continental Margins Group
225 from the Institute of Marine Science, ICM-CSIC, and were conducted onboard the Spanish
226 research vessels García del CID, Hespérides; Sarmiento de Gamboa and Angeles Alvariño. The
227 seismic profiles have different resolutions (high and ultrahigh) and utilize different techniques:
228 multi-channel seismic (MCS), single channel and parametric. Multi-channel seismic profiles
229 were downloaded from the Spanish Hydrocarbon Technical Archive
230 (<https://geoportal.minetur.gob.es/ATHv2/welcome.do>) and they are commercial data from oil
231 companies. These profiles have a vertical standard resolution of tens of meters with a penetration
232 of up to 10 seconds. The single-channel profiles were obtained with airgun systems (140 to 530
233 c.i.), have an average vertical resolution of < 15 m of few meters time with a penetration of up to
234 <3s seconds. The parametric seismic profiles were acquired with the TOPAS (TOPographic
235 Parametric Echosounder) whose vertical resolution is about <30±40 cm within the upper 150 ms
236 of the sediment column. The seismic lines were integrated into a IHS Kingdom project for their
237 correlation and interpretation.

238

239 The swath bathymetric data were recorded with a SIMRAD EM120 multibeam
240 echosounder with a frequency of 12 kHz. Multi-beam bathymetry datasets independent to this
241 study were also compiled and integrated for the present study. These bathymetries were obtained
242 from the MARSIBAL and Fauces 1bis projects and the Fishing General Secretary (Spanish
243 Government). The data are available at a repository
244 (<http://gma.icm.csic.es/sites/default/files/geoweb/OLsurveys/index.htm>). The [Global Mapper](#)
245 software, a versatile GIS application from Blue Marble Geographics, was selected for integrating
246 all those bathymetries in order to generate a gridded bathymetric map at 50 m. The vertical
247 resolution was approximately 0.025% of the water depth. The mapping of the Averroes Fault
248 trace and its analysis on the multibeam map was also done with drawing and measurement tools
249 in [Global Mapper](#) and IHS Kingdom project.

250

251 For plotting the epicentre locations at the seafloor of the Alboran Sea, the seismicity
252 database of the Spanish National Geographic Institute (IGN) (www.ign.es) was used. The
253 epicentre datasets were plotted on the multibeam bathymetric map using visualization tools from
254 the Global Mapper.

255

256 **Chronostratigraphy**

257

258 The available scientific well information for the study area (ODP Site 977) was
259 integrated into the IHS Kingdom project with seismic lines for their chronostratigraphy
260 correlation and interpretation. A precise chronology of the seismic stratigraphic boundaries was
261 developed through an age calibration based primarily on data from that Site (Fig. S1). In order to
262 confirm the chronology, the chronostratigraphic boundaries were also correlated with those in
263 commercial and scientific wells for across the entire Alboran Basin³¹. The velocity-to-depth (ms
264 to m) conversion was performed using the speed of sound (1500 m/s) for the parametric profiles
265 (Fig. S1) and a weighted average velocity (1779 m/s) from ODP Site 976³² for the multi- and
266 single-channel profiles.

267

268 **The Averroes Fault rate of tectonic activity**

269 The average vertical slip rate (0.1 mm/yr) results from divide the vertical offset (470 m)
270 by the age of the oldest materials affected by the Averroes Fault (4.57 myr). In the same way, the
271 averaged period of fault recurrence (31,000 yr) has been calculated dividing the oldest known
272 age (124,060 yr) by the number of fault events (4).

273

274 **Seafloor deformation**

275 The crustal deformation at the seafloor generated by a given earthquake along the
276 Averroes Fault was computed using the Coulomb 3.3 code^{33,34}, in which calculations were
277 performed using an established approach^{25,26} assuming an elastic half-space with uniform elastic
278 properties. The fault was modelled using different vertical planes to better fit the curved
279 geometry of the fault trace. All of these planes extended from the surface of the seafloor to a
280 depth of 10 km, where the majority of hypocentres near the Averroes Fault are located. Typical
281 values of 0.25 for Poisson's ratio and 8×10^{25} bar for Young's modulus were applied.

282

283 **Tsunami model**

284 Tsunami-Hyperbolic Systems and Efficient Algorithms (Tsunami-HySEA)^{35,36} is a finite-
285 volume numerical model that solves the 2D non-linear shallow water equations in spherical
286 coordinates. It has been developed by the EDANYA group of the University of Malaga
287 specifically for simulations of seismically induced tsunamis. This model, based on a graphic
288 processing unit (GPU) architecture, is robust, reliable and accurate. The combination of this kind
289 of numerical model with an efficient GPU results in a faster than real-time (FTRT) numerical
290 model capable of simulating the generation, propagation and inundation of a tsunami in a region
291 covered by a grid with several million cells in only a few minutes. This model has been
292 extensively validated under the standard benchmarks proposed by the National Tsunami Hazards
293 Mitigation Program (NTHMP) of the U.S.A.^{37,38} and has been extensively tested in several
294 scenarios and compared with other well-established tsunami models^{39,40}.

295 Tsunami-HySEA has been implemented using CUDA and MPI in order to take advantage
296 of the massive parallel architecture of multi-GPU clusters, so that the computing time required

297 could be dramatically reduced with respect to the use of a single CPU core or even a multi-core
298 processor and, at the same time, numerical resolution could be increased still computing
299 extremely fast. Many features are included in Tsunami-HySEA, such as the possibility of using
300 nested meshes, direct output of time series, the computation of the initial seafloor deformation
301 using the Okada (1992) model, support for rectangular or triangular faults, etc. A 2D domain
302 decomposition is performed, and load balancing techniques are also used considering the wet and
303 dry zones and the nested meshes, so that the computational load of all the MPI processes is as
304 similar as possible. The entire numerical computation is carried out in multi-GPUs, using double
305 numerical precision, including the nested meshes processing. Multiple CUDA kernels have been
306 implemented, and CUDA streams are used to compute in parallel different meshes in a same
307 level of the grid hierarchy. Furthermore, the MPI communications can overlap with kernel
308 computations and memory transfers between CPU and GPU memory in order to increase the
309 efficiency of the solver. By means of this very efficient implementation, the model is able to
310 simulate 8 hours of real time tsunami in the Mediterranean Sea (in a mesh with 10 million
311 volumes and a resolution of 30 arc-sec) in 257 seconds using two NVIDIA Tesla P100, or even
312 in 284 seconds with one NVIDIA Tesla V100.

313 The topobathymetric ambient grid covers the Alboran Sea from 5.0°W to 1.8353°W and
314 35.0598°N to 36.8499°N (Fig.4) with a resolution of 1.611 arc-sec (~50 m). The ambient grid
315 contains 28.284 million cells. Six high-resolution nested grids with a resolution of 0.201 arc-sec
316 (~6 m) and 52.522 million cells, has been defined along the Spanish coasts where the impact of
317 the tsunami is more important (Fig. S3).

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459

460 **Author contributions**

461 F.E., J.G. and G.E conceived the idea for the study and wrote the paper with
462 methodological contributions from J.G.V. in the tsunami mathematical model and J.P. in the
463 seafloor deformation and tsunami potential. The geodynamic framework and fault
464 characterization was done by F.E., J.G. and J.V., while the chronostratigraphic correlation with
465 ODP sites was carry out by F.E. and G.E.. All these authors designed and performed the specific
466 oceanographic cruises to study the Averroes Fault and its geologic context. F.E. also processed
467 and compiled the seismic profiles and well data, integrating them into a IHS Kingdom project.
468 J.P. calculated the seafloor deformation and tsunami potential model. The propagation tsunami
469 model was done by J.G.V., J.M. and S.O. as well as associated figures and videos. All authors
470 provided guidance on the analyses and commented on the manuscript.

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472 **Additional information**

473 The authors declare no competing interests.